

**GIPERGEOMETRIK FUNKSIYA VA UNI ANALITIK DAVOM
ETTIRISHGA OID VA BOSHQA BA'ZI FORMULALAR**

**O'zbekiston Respublikasi IIV Qoraqalpoq akademik litsey
matematika fani o'qituvchisi
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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada gipergeometrik funksiyani analitik davom ettirishga oid va boshqa ba'zi formulalar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: formulalar, gipergeometrik funksiya, kadrlar tayyorlash, formula, integral, Gauss tenglama, gipergeometrik qator.

KIRISH

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti I.A.Karimov Oliy Majlisning XIV sessiyasida so'zlagan nutqida kadrlar tayyorlashning ahamiyatiga izoh berib shunday degan edi:

«Biz oldimizga qanday vazifa qo'ymaylik, qanday muammoni yechish zaruriyati tug'ilmasin, gap oxir oqibat, baribir kadrlarga borib qadalaveradi. Mubolag'asiz aytish mumkinki, bizning kelajagimiz, mamlakatimiz kelajagi, o'rnimizga kim kelishiga yoki boshqacharoq qilib aytganda, qanday kadrlar tayyorlashimizga bog'liq.

Mamlakatimiz kelajagi uchun Oliy Majlisning IX sessiyasida qabul qilingan «Kadrlar tayyorlash bo'yicha milliy dasturi»ning amalga oshirilishi juda ham muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Endi gipergeometrik funksiyaning $x=1$ dagi qiymatini hisoblaymiz. Shu maqsadda, (6) formuladagi integral $b>0$, $c>0$ va $|x|<1$ bo'lganda tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'lgani sababli $x \rightarrow 1$ da limitga o'tamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} F(a, b, c; x) &= \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-xt)^{-a} dt = \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \left[t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-xt)^{-a} \right] dt = \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-a-b-1} dt = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} B(b, c-a-b) = \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \frac{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)} = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)}. \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 1} F(a, b, c; x) = F(a, b, c; 1) = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)}.$$

Agar (6) formuladagi integralda

$$t = \frac{1-s}{1-xs} \text{ yoki } s = \frac{1-t}{1-xt}$$

almashtirish bajarsak, integral quyidagi ko‘rinishda yoziladi:

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-xt)^{-a} dt = \\ &= (1-x)^{c-a-b} \int_0^1 s^{c-b-1} (1-s)^{b-1} (1-xs)^{-(c-a)} ds = \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)}{\Gamma(c)} (1-x)^{c-a-b} F(c-a, c-b, c; x). \end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$F(a, b, c; x) = (1-x)^{c-a-b} F(c-a, c-b, c; x). \quad (7)$$

Bu tenglik avtotransformatsiya formulasi deyiladi.

$F(a, b, c; x) = F(b, a, c; x)$ tenglikni e‘tiborga olib, (6) tenglikni

$$F(a, b, c; x) = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(c-a)} \int_0^1 t^{a-1} (1-t)^{c-a-1} (1-xt)^{-b} dt$$

kabi yozib olamiz va integralda $t = 1-s$ almashtirish bajaramiz:

$$F(a, b, c; x) = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(c-a)} (1-x)^{-b} \int_0^1 s^{c-a-1} (1-s)^{a-1} \left(1 - \frac{x}{x-1} s\right)^{-b} ds.$$

Bu yerdagi integralni (6) bilan taqqoslab,

$$F(a, b, c; x) = (1-x)^{-b} F\left(c-a, b, c; \frac{x}{x-1}\right) \quad (8)$$

formulaga ega bo‘lamiz. Bundan $c = a$ da

$$F(a, b, a; x) = (1-x)^{-b}$$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Agar $x < 1/2$ bo‘lsa, $|x/(x-1)| < 1$ bo‘ladi. Bunda (8) tenglikning o‘ng tomonidagi gipergeometrik funksiya, tegishli gipergeometrik qatorning yig‘indisi sifatida qaralishi mumkin [1]. Demak, (8) formula $F(a, b, c; x)$ funksiyani $-\infty < x < -1$ oraliqqa analitik davom ettiradi.

(8) tenglikda x ni $(1-x)$ ga almashtirib, uning boshqa ko‘rinishiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$F(a, b, c; 1-x) = x^{-b} F\left(c-a, b, c; \frac{x-1}{x}\right). \quad (9)$$

Gipergeometrik funksiyaning $-1 \leq x \leq 1$ kesmadan tashqarida aniqlashga xizmat qiluvchi boshqa formulalarni ham keltirib chiqaraylik.

Avval x va $1-x$ argumentli gipergeometrik funksiyalar orasidagi munosabatni topamiz. $|x| < 1$ va $|1-x|$ intervallar kesishmasida (1) tenglamaning $y_1(x) = F(a, b, c; -x)$ yechimi uning y_3 va y_4 yechimlari chiziqli kombinatsiyasi sifatida ifodalanadi, ya’ni

$$F(a, b, c; x) = AF(a, b, a+b-c+1; 1-x) + B(1-x)^{c-a-b} F(c-a, c-b, c-a-b+1; 1-x), \quad c-a-b \notin \mathbb{Z}. \quad (10)$$

Bu yerda a, b, c parametrlarning (10) tenglikdagi barcha gipergeometrik funksiyalar mahnoga ega bo‘ladigan qiymatlari qaraladi.

$x=1$ bo'lganda (10) tenglamaning o'ng tomoni a, b, c parametrlarning ixtiyoriy qiymatlarida mahnoga ega, chap tomoni chekli bo'lishi esa $c-a-b$ ning ishorasiga bog'liq. Agar $c-a-b > 0$ bo'lsa, (10) dan $x=1$ da

$$A = F(a, b, c; 1) = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)} \quad (11)$$

kelib chiqadi. Agar $c-a-b < 0$ bo'lsa, (10) ning chap tomoniga (7) formulani qo'llab, so'ngra hosil bo'lgan tenglikni $(1-x)^{a+b-c}$ ga ko'paytirib va $x=1$ deb

$$B = F(c-a, c-b, c; 1) = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(a+b-c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)} \quad (12)$$

ekanligini topamiz.

(11) va (12) tengliklarga asosan (10) tenglikni

$$\begin{aligned} F(a, b, c; x) &= \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)} F(a, b, a+b-c+1, 1-x) + \\ &+ \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(a+b-c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)} (1-x)^{c-a-b} F(c-a, c-b, c-a-b+1; 1-x), \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad c-a-b \notin \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. (8) ning o'ng tomoniga (13) formulani qo'llab, quyidagi formulaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} F(a, b, c; x) &= \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(b-a)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(b)} (1-x)^{-a} F\left(a, c-b, a-b+1; \frac{1}{1-x}\right) + \\ &+ \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(a-b)}{\Gamma(c-b)\Gamma(a)} (1-x)^{-b} F\left(c-a, b, b-a+1; \frac{1}{1-x}\right), a-b \notin \mathbb{Z}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Agar (8) va (13) tengliklarning o'ng tomoniga mos ravishda (14) va (9) formulalarni qo'llasak,

$$F(a, b, c; x) = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(b-a)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(b)} (-x)^{-a} F\left(a, a-c+1, a-b+1; \frac{1}{x}\right) +$$

$$+\frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(a-b)}{\Gamma(c-b)\Gamma(a)}(-x)^{-b}F\left(b,b-c+1,b-a+1;\frac{1}{x}\right), a-b \notin \mathbb{Z}; \quad (15)$$

$$F(a,b,c;x) = \frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(c-a-b)}{\Gamma(c-a)\Gamma(c-b)}x^{-a}F\left(a,a-c+1,a+b-c+1;\frac{x-1}{x}\right) +$$

$$+\frac{\Gamma(c)\Gamma(a+b-c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)}x^{a-c}(1-x)^{c-a-b}F\left(c-a,1-a,c-a-b+1;\frac{x-1}{x}\right),$$

$$c-a-b \notin \mathbb{Z} \quad (16)$$

tengliklar kelib chiqadi.

(13), (14), (15), (16) tengliklar gipergeometrik funksiyani mos ravishda $|1-x| < 1$, $|1-x| > 1$, $|x| > 1$, $|(1-x)/x| < 1$ tengsizliklar bilan *aniqlanuvchi oraliqlarga analitik davomini beradi*. (13) - odatda *Bolts formulasi* deb ataladi.

Quyidagi tenglik $c = a + b$ bo'lganda gipergeometrik funksiyaning $x = 1$ nuqta atrofidagi xulqini ifodalaydi [1]:

$$F(a,b,a+b;1-x) = -\frac{\Gamma(a+b)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)}F(a,b,1;x)\ln x +$$

$$+\frac{\Gamma(a+b)}{\Gamma^2(a)\Gamma^2(b)}\sum_{k=0}^{\infty}\frac{\Gamma(a+k)\Gamma(b+k)}{(k!)^2}\left[2\cdot\frac{\Gamma'(1+k)}{\Gamma(1+k)} - \frac{\Gamma'(a+k)}{\Gamma(a+k)} - \frac{\Gamma'(b+k)}{\Gamma(b+k)}\right]x^k.$$

Gipergeometrik funksiyalar uchun quyidagi tengliklar ham o'rinli [1]:

$$1. F(a,1-a,c;x) = (1-x)^{c-1}F\left(\frac{c-a}{2},\frac{c+a-1}{2},c;4x(1-x)\right);$$

$$2. F(a,1-a,c;-x) = (1+x)^{c-1}\left(\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{x}\right)^{2-2a-2c} \times$$

$$\times F\left[c+a-1,c-1/2,2c-1;4\sqrt{x(1+x)}\left(\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{x}\right)^{-2}\right];$$

$$3. F\left(2a,2b,a+b+\frac{1}{2};x\right) = F\left[a,b,a+b+\frac{1}{2};4x(1-x)\right];$$

$$4. F\left(a, b, a + b + \frac{1}{2}; x\right) = F\left(2a, 2b, a + b + \frac{1}{2}; \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{1-x}\right) = \\ = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{1-x}\right)^{-2a} F\left(2a, a - b + \frac{1}{2}, a + b + \frac{1}{2}; \frac{\sqrt{1-x}-1}{\sqrt{1-x}+1}\right).$$

$$5. F\left(a - \frac{1}{2}, a, 2a; x\right) = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{1-x}\right)^{1-2a}$$

$$6. F\left(2a, 2b, a + b + \frac{1}{2}; \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{\Gamma(a + b + 1/2)\Gamma(1/2)}{\Gamma(a + 1/2)\Gamma(b + 1/2)}, a + b + \frac{1}{2} \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$$

Izoh. 2-, 3- va 4- badda keltirilgan formulalarni $\{z\} = \{x + iy\}$ kompleks o'zgaruvchi tekisligida ham qarash mumkin. Bunda ba'zi formulalarga qo'shimcha cheklanishlar kelib chiqadi.

Xulosa

Ma'lumki, aksariyat maxsus funksiyalar ma'lum bir differensial tenglamaning maxsus nuqtasi atrofidagi yechimidan iborat bo'ladi. Shulardan biri bo'lgan gipergeometrik funksiya Gauss tenglamasining yechimi bo'lib, u o'z argumenti $-1 < x < 1$ bo'lganda aniq bir qatorning yig'indisidan iboratdir. Lekin matematikada bu funksiyaning bu oraliqdan tashqaridagi qiymatlaridan foydalanish qulay bo'ladi. Buni amalga oshirish uchun $-1 < x < 1$ oraliqda aniqlangan funksiyani bu oraliqdan chetga analitik davom ettirishga to'g'ri keladi. Bunda funksiyaning $-1 < x < 1$ oraliqda o'rinli bo'lgan xossalariidan foydalangan holda amalga oshiriladi.

Mazkur kurs ishimda ana shu fikrlarga amal qilgan holda $F(a, b, c; x)$ gipergeometrik funksiyaning turli xossalari bayon qilingan. Jumladan, differensiallash qoidalari, qo'shish qoidalari, integral ko'rinishlari va h.k. Albatta matematikaning rivojida bu funksiyani turli yo'nalishlardagi umumlashmalarini bilish ham qoniqarlidir.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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